

Wearables Technology: Awareness, Adoption and Applications in Indian Health Insurance Industry.

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Abstract

Wearable technology for the general public is still in its infancy, although it has advanced rapidly in recent years. Health insurers have been closely studying the potential use of these devices since their inception, and gadgets that can measure and collect various types of health data have piqued their interest.

This study looks at the deployment and practical applications of wearables in the health insurance business. We examine why insurers are considering using wearable devices, how they might improve their business models, and how to avoid some common pitfalls. The wearable devices are touted to provide exact and detailed real-time data. This research investigates public perceptions of wearable technology and its possible applications. This research also discusses the financial implications of incorporating wearables into an insurance policy, as well as other critical considerations when employing wearable data. While wearable data can help insurers get fresh insights into their members' overall fitness habits, the application element of the health insurance premium still has some mystery. This paper also tries to illustrate how the product development phase in health insurance may be improved and how personalized goods can be offered.

As part of the research, a market survey was conducted to better understand consumer perceptions of wearables and possible ideas on their applicability in the field of health insurance, i.e., Awareness levels of the general public of the potential uses and applications of wearables in the insurance industry. The market research findings are included in the report,

along with explanations of some of the most significant findings. Even though many of the respondents owned a wearable gadget and some of them have kept track of their health data. Their views on the usage of wearable data in insurance were rather varied. The diversity of devices utilized by survey participants, their familiarity with some of the wearable devices, and the benefits they hope to gain from utilizing the wearable devices are all taken into account in this research. The study explores the link between educational attainment, age, and income earned. The impact of wearable technologies on consciousness is examined and analyzed in-depth in this report.

Keywords: Wearable Technology, Telemedicine, Healthcare, Insurance, India

1.1 Introduction

In India, the health insurance market is the fastest expanding non-life insurance sector. In FY 17, the total non-life insurance business saw a healthy growth percentage of 24 percent, with a share in the market of 24 percent. For the previous ten years, it has been the quickest expanding sector, with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 23%. There is a big opportunity for health insurance to expand and reach a larger population.

More and more private health insurers are coming into the market to deliver better health services to a larger segment of the population, with personalized health care coverage. Although COVID-19 has led to unparalleled disruption in every sector, it can be said that the health insurance industry has seen this as an opportunity in a way.

More innovations in marketing health insurance are required. The healthcare business has been cautious to adopt digital tools in the past; innovation is now critical to recouping from the losses sustained during the pandemic. Even during the pandemic, when we were all imprisoned inside our houses, digital media played an important role in keeping the world unified. Healthcare technology and digital solutions have a much broader impact than we could have anticipated. There are various examples of using digital techniques to overcome a problem during these difficult times.

In the Indian healthcare industry, word of mouth has always been the most effective marketing tactic, but that is no longer the case. Typically, as statistics demonstrate, the young generation is the most active on social and digital platforms. During the pandemic, however, even the elderly population used telemedicine. As a result, healthcare professionals saw the need to improve services such as online appointment booking and consultations, e-prescriptions, and pharmaceutical delivery to patients' homes. They now realize that this is the way to go in terms of attracting, treating, and retaining patients.

Another benefit of digital health is the ease with which people can get it. However, in our country, a substantial portion of the population is still not linked to the internet. As a result, this is an issue that should be addressed at all levels of the healthcare industry.

According to estimates, the number of linked wearable gadgets on the market will exceed 1000 million by 2022. Wearable devices have the potential to improve population health by shifting the focus from disease treatment to prevention; routinely monitoring personalized physiological measurements; supporting self-management; identifying changes in health conditions; and creating positive long-term behavioral changes toward healing. Despite these advantages, it is unclear whether wearable-based innovations will be successful in the healthcare sector, because external forces such as funding, technology, key industry players, government policy customers, and accountability can instill or kill wearable-based innovations, among other things. See Fig 1.1 showing the rise of wearable devices.

Fig 1.1: Rise of wearable devices

Source: Statista 2021 (<https://www.statista.com/>)

In the case of health insurance, wearable device insights could lead to a more customer-centric model that anticipates customers' risks and demands, enabling new use cases such as continuous risk assessment, prediction of future health insurance claims, personalized insights to promote disease prevention, targeted marketing, customer engagement, and claims management.

In reality, wearables are gaining traction in group insurance through employers. Health insurance companies like Max Bupa, Bajaj Allianz Humana, and Manipal Cigna, for example, have created initiatives to encourage the usage of wearable devices in the workplace. In general,

health insurance firms use wearable devices to encourage workplace wellness and prevention and track progress; in exchange for healthy behaviors, businesses receive financial incentives such as decreased group premiums in their health insurance policy.

Previous researches have emphasized that health insurance companies could adjust their product strategies to incentivize individuals to use wearable devices, as well as determining whether customers would be willing to use a wearable device and share data with their health or life insurance business in exchange for financial rewards. However, little is known regarding people's willingness to adopt wearable device-based health insurance plans, and their awareness about it, especially those that go beyond health promotion.

Therefore, the main goal of this study is to evaluate the mindset of the population to adopt wearables and the level of awareness people possess about the devices as looking from an Indian perspective, as we do not have comprehensive and dedicated data protection legislation till now. An additional goal is to explore the applications of these wearables in the health insurance sector and more about the economic incentives for these devices.

Objectives

This study in a broader context addresses the issue of how the technology has aided the new players in the industry to propel themselves beyond the usual aspect of selling insurance and also whether the corresponding measurable data provided from the measurable devices are likely to enhance the pricing mechanics in Health insurers premiums significantly. What all factors affect the risk assessment criteria of Insurers and how fraud detection and procurement of accurate data can be performed.

The technology acceptance among adults is also discussed here. Their demographics, work, and organizational characteristics and their experience with wearables, and also their willingness to use wearables will be covered. Whether there are drastic changes or it doesn't have much of an effect on the daily routine of the users. The acceptance of wearable devices among the public will also be inferred at the end of the project.

The wearable technology market has skyrocketed in 5 years in India, but only a few pieces of research have shed some light on why people use them. Awareness of these devices among the common public has to be investigated and how familiar are they with the incentives and applications these devices provide. The research objective that is devised is based upon the awareness of the Indian population about Wearable technology. India is still in its initial stages of implementing a privacy IT law, this research is important in understanding the general public's notion about the involvement of these devices in their daily life.

The research objectives are planned based on the following questions.

- Do people in a developing country like India have adequate information required to be a part of something that transmits real-time data to an unknown entity according to them?
- How willing are the customers in using the wearables?
- Has Wearable tech improved the health habits, lifestyle, and productivity of the customers?
- What are the most important attributes they wish to measure using the Technology?
- Is the insurance premium discount a primary incentive for someone to use a wearable?

This study was conducted by collecting data from customers using a self-made questionnaire to measure the different attributes of wearable device users and how knowledgeable they are on the applications of the devices. Questionnaire formulation was based upon the above points as to how the whole wearable technology has altered the health insurance dimensions and by showing the customers both the advantages and disadvantages of the technology will the customers still be willing to purchase the devices if offered at a reasonable price range.

The scope of the study encompasses reaching out to participants who may or may not own a piece of wearable technology and enquiring about the awareness about the technology and what the incentives they wish to obtain if the insurers use the data for pricing mechanism. The awareness tends to decrease with the increase in age wearable devices are being discussed which brings in the personalized form of the insurance sector. People will have tailor-made insurance plans that will have to be paid as they live.

This project tries to reduce the uncertainty among whether or not one owns a device. The number of health-related wearable devices is increasing but it is not clear if people are willing to adopt these wearables and the potential incentives. The applications of the Insurers and stakeholders that whether the general public are ready to welcome wearable technology to their lifestyle and obtain incentives from it. This will open a wide range of opportunities for the

insurers for personalized insurance products. The limitations of the study will be because of the limited time and money constraints. Insights are taken from the customer interactions during the internship period about the awareness of the devices. To achieve alignment with relevant stakeholders, insurers must examine both their own goals and those of stakeholders and regulators. To ensure that they can offer effective insurance products, they will also need to assess their consumers' needs and define their operational and technological capabilities.

Consumer-grade wearables are beginning to resemble medical-grade wearables in that they can now capture more accurate vital health data. Apple, for example, has promised that its consumer-grade products will be adapted to monitor hypertension and diabetes.

The market is debating whether consumer-grade wearables or medical-grade gadgets should be used. Consumer-grade gadgets such as Fitbit and Garmin are used to track steps, activity, and sleep. Medical-grade gadgets keep track of more detailed and comprehensive health data. We tend to look at solutions for wearables that are tied to consumer-grade wearables that are on the market and that people use when we're looking for them. Insurers look at a variety of data points, including exercise, steps, and heart rate, as well as sleep to a lesser extent. Other characteristics, such as mood and eating habits, might be monitored via gadgets.

Fig 1.2 Stakeholder Alignment for Viable Insurance products

Source: Milliman Report, March,2020 (<https://www.milliman.com/>)

Review of Literature

Wearable technologies make it possible to track human physical activities and behaviors, as well as physiological and biochemical markers, in real-time. Through the use of electrocardiogram (ECG), ballistocardiogram (BCG), and other equipment, vital indicators such as heart rate, blood pressure, and body temperature, as well as blood oxygen saturation, posture, and physical activities, are the most regularly measured data. Providing care for an elderly population has become a big concern in many countries. For example, the number of Americans aged 65 and up is expected to increase from around 53 million in 2021 to around 100 million in 2060. (*Vespa, Armstrong, & Medina, 2018*).

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that by 2050, the global aged population would have risen to 2 billion people (WHO, 2015). Chronic diseases, falls, impairments, and other negative health consequences are more common among the elderly (*Ambrose, Paul, & Hausdorff, 2013*). Preventive therapies for the elderly to improve health outcomes have become an exciting area in research and development. Wearable technology could help solve some of the problems associated with recognizing and managing bad health issues in the elderly.

The insurance industry is ripe with opportunities for analytics. It applies to every aspect of an insurance company's operations. (*Peter Fader and Mike Nemeth 2016*). But what we're seeing now isn't just a want to do a better job; it's also a need to know how good of a job I'm doing for my consumers. As a result, analytics is concentrating on measures like customer satisfaction and Net Promoter Score as a way of gauging how well companies are performing. Then, once they've determined how well they're performing, they can fine-tune their efforts to improve their Net Promoter Rankings and customer satisfaction scores. As a result, you get a closed-loop effect where you run analytics in advance, test those analytics, measure, and then alter your behavior as you move forward. Wearable technologies have a lot of potential for preventing falls among the elderly. Each year, 30 percent to 60 percent of older persons fall, with 10% to 20% of those falling resulting in injury, hospitalization, or death (*Rubenstein, 2006*). Two out of every three Americans would embrace health insurance wellness programs based on wearable devices provided the economic, data privacy, and technical conditions were right, especially if the advantages were tied to health promotion and primary prevention. As a result, health insurance wellness programs based on wearable devices could be a crucial incentive strategy for health insurers to appeal to the younger and healthier sectors of the population, thereby keeping them and stabilizing risk pool insurance costs.

Wearables in medical insurance situations are largely used to improve claim cost forecasts, make members healthier, and reduce total claim frequency and amounts, all while increasing an insurer's competitive position. (*Lalit Baveja, Samyukta Achar 2020*). According to Rao et al., wearable gadgets are being utilized by insurance companies to help increase earnings, sales opportunities, and lower customer retention and acquisition costs. For this, Big Data and Wearables in Life Insurance provide businesses with a more focused strategy to attract and maintain customers. Many businesses have embraced wearable technology to entice customers

to utilize this gadget, which records personal data such as physical activity, blood pressure, BMI, heart rate, and so on. They set goals for consumers to meet within a certain time frame, which assists customers in keeping a healthy lifestyle and living a better life, as well as assisting customers in receiving benefits from insurance companies. In addition, Big Data assists insurance businesses in identifying new business prospects and expanding customer relationships for increased profitability.

Data plays an essential role in the insurance sector, according to Data is gathered from a variety of sources, including wearable devices with sensors, social media activity, voice analysis, and more. Many insurance companies are looking into how they can use this data in conjunction with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to solve business challenges in the insurance industry, such as underwriting, claim handling, fraud detection and prevention, pricing, sales, and customer experience. Additionally, they are investigating how to employ predictive modeling and machine learning to improve customer happiness, business efficiency, and operations. e. In addition, some of the issues that insurers may experience as a result of adopting this technology are connected to data security in an insurance firm, which must be addressed.

When looking at how smart wearables with AI techniques are used in the field of healthcare, specifically health insurance, it is discovered that it assists the healthcare system in obtaining information about a person's health, exercise patterns, and predicting early diseases for better future health. This highlights how an insurance firm may use a wearable gadget to alter their customer relationships to grow their business and profit. (*Apeksha Shah et al 2021*) This research paves the way for researchers, insurance domain specialists, and healthcare practitioners to figure out how the data gathered from end-users may be used to provide value to customers and insurance companies by developing a health-aware ecosystem. This, however, will be complicated by privacy problems that must be addressed. Exploring the far-reaching implications can also aid in the reduction of false claims and the rapid and reasonable settlement of claims.

(Daniel Thyssen et al.) employ predictive analysis to investigate how wearables are useful and used in the insurance industry. It demonstrates how predictive modeling, handwritten recognition, text analytics, and data capture may be used to improve business processing. Wearable devices, the Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, Cognitive Technology, and other new technologies can aid with this. It can assist insurance companies with claim processing, dynamic pricing, better underwriting, and reserving decisions by using predictive modeling. These predictive modeling techniques can be performed with the help of wearable devices that are consolidated with sensors that collect data from the human body and include several advantages such as managing diseases at an early stage, reducing claims in an insurance company by meeting an insurer's goal, better rehabilitation, and so on.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming the way insurance companies interact with their customers, according to (Samad Masood et al.) AI has proved useful in detecting fraud for many years, but insurers are now using these technologies for other purposes, such as

increasing operational efficiency. Insurers are combining the Internet of Things with artificial intelligence to boost operational efficiency and client experiences. Many businesses have begun to use artificial intelligence (AI) to assist with ad hoc insurance claims. Aside from that, AI is used in the insurance industry for a variety of purposes, including prediction, pricing, processing, personalization, and prevention measures. Several organizations are employing wearable electronics to assist customers to attain some physical activity by setting goals and then offering different claims, discounts, and wellness benefits with insurance based on the outcomes. As a result, this was still a challenge. Because data is so vital, insurance companies must design a data plan for data security.

In medical insurance, wearables are largely used to improve claim cost forecasts, make members healthier, and reduce total claim frequency and amounts, all while enhancing an insurer's competitive position. (*Joanne Buckle, Tanya Hayward, Natasha Singhal And Kishan Desai Mar 2020*). However, at present, there is insufficient proof that wearables have an impact on consumers' long-term habits. There is also scant evidence that metrics gathered by wearables today are powerful influencers of long-term lifestyle, and it is important to know that wearable technology alone is doubtful to drive radical reform in healthy behaviors and alter individuals' health statuses.

Although wearables provide a range of health statistics and therefore significant extra evaluation parameters for underwriting and pricing reasons, the most purported consequence has its own set of risks, and the added complexity of combining these data pieces may not be justified. Potential dangers must be addressed, such as tracking inaccurate information or falsified data. Furthermore, the diversity of data from various devices is an issue. Although real-time data is an added advantage for big data configurations, it must be used with caution due to the high risk of fraud, high potential costs for insurers, questionable data accuracy, and concerns about fairness in how this translates into pricing and underwriting decisions that affect individual members. But in the Indian scenario, the willingness and awareness of the population to accept wearable technology in their daily lives are not much put into scrutiny.

Methods

The main objective of the project was to study wearable technology and its applications and awareness among the public wherein the tool used for data collection was a structured questionnaire. It was chosen to clearly understand trends in the market and also to gather uniform insights from the customers to generalize the strategies for the area. The questionnaire served the purpose of an initial survey and general analysis of the market.

The market survey was done as part of the study to gain a better understanding of consumer perceptions of wearables and people's ideas in using them in insurance. The results of the market research are presented and explained are some of the most important discoveries. Even

while many of the respondents were tracking their health data and some of them were part of the insurance sector, their perspectives in using the tracking data in insurance were fairly diverse. This project has taken into account the variety of tracking devices owned by respondents, the nature and regularity of activity recorded, and respondents' opinions on how this data is utilized to set premiums for their insurance plans.

In this research, we used Google forms to collect data and it was circulated to the sample population. As due to Covid 19 pandemic we could not have face to face interaction. The survey got 163 responses in return and the responses were analyzed through the software package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) and inferences were drawn out of it.

The survey was performed using a google forms link shared via personal messages, LinkedIn, email, and other social networking sites inside the researcher's connections and network to make respondents think about wearables in insurance in light of their role as "consumers". They were asked questions like:

- Demographic profile
- Use of Wearable devices in their daily life
- Thoughts insurers accessing their health tracking data with their consent
- Opinions on the agreement of using tracking data to calculate premiums
- Opinions on the making use of discounts for wearing wearables when renewing an insurance policy

Questionnaire formulation can be based upon the above points as to how the whole wearable technology has altered the health insurance dimensions and by showing the customers both the advantages and disadvantages of the technology will the customers still be willing to purchase the devices if offered at a reasonable price range.

For the research, a sample of 61 people termed millennials (age 22-38) was drawn through convenience sampling.

In this research process, the convenience sample selected was 163 people. The convenience sample included the individuals who happen to be most accessible to the researchers.

Hypothesis

Awareness of Wearable devices

Independent variables:

- Degree of Education
- Monthly Income
- Owning a health insurance policy

Dependent Variable:

- Awareness about Wearables

Table 1.1: Hypothesis formulation

Hypothesis	Description
H1	The degree of education significantly influence customer awareness of wearable devices
H2	Monthly Income have an impact on customer awareness of wearable devices
H3	There is no significant difference in awareness of wearable devices of people owning a health insurance policy

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of Respondents

52.8 % of respondents belonged to the age group of 18-29 years. The majority of respondents (76%) were male & 48.5 % of respondents were single. 44.2 % of respondents were salaried employees. 27% of the respondents preferred not to talk about their income category.

Table 1.2: Demographic profile of Respondents

S.No	Groups	Frequency	Percentage
Age			
1	18 - 29	86	52.8
2	30 - 39	24	14.7
3	40 - 49	14	8.6
4	50 & above	39	23.9
Gender			
1	Male	124	76.1
2	Female	38	23.9
The highest degree of Education			
1	High School education	0	0
2	Higher Secondary School	1	0.6
3	Undergraduate	37	22.7
4	Postgraduate	66.9	109
5	Higher	16	9.8

Employment Status			
1	Self-employed	25	15.3
2	Salaried Employee	72	44.2
3	Student	57	35
4	Looking for work	5	3.1
5	Retired	3	1.8
6	Other	1	0.6
Monthly Income			
1	Less than Rs. 10000	25	15.3
2	Rs 10001 - Rs 25000	9	5.5
3	Rs 25001 - Rs 50000	20	12.3
4	Rs 50001 - Rs 1 Lakh	16	9.8
5	More than Rs 1 Lakh	49	30.1
6	Prefer not to answer	44	27

The quantitative data were analyzed and the tests applied during the research were:

- Independent sample T-test
- ANOVA (Analysis of variance)

Since a combination of 2 tests were to be used the data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software and the output and model summary were derived from the same. SPSS provided a perfect graphical representation of the data and also an appropriate result for the data that had been entered. The software helped in providing high accuracy of results and quality decision-making.

Testing of Hypothesis

H1: Degree of education significantly influence the customer awareness of wearable devices

Table 1.3 Descriptive Statistics: The effects of degree of education on awareness of wearable devices

Descriptives

WearableDevice

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
2.0	1	3.00	3	3
3.0	37	3.49	1.017	.167	3.15	3.83	2	5
4.0	109	3.48	.968	.093	3.29	3.66	1	5
5.0	16	2.94	1.063	.266	2.37	3.50	1	5
Total	163	3.42	.993	.078	3.27	3.58	1	5

ANOVA

WearableDevice

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.418	3	1.473	1.507	.215
Within Groups	155.373	159	.977		
Total	159.791	162			

Table 1.4. Testing Hypothesis using ANOVA

A one-way ANOVA between subjects was conducted to compare the effects of degree of education on awareness of wearable devices on customers. We chose ANOVA because it is an appropriate test for multiple test subjects. There was a significant effect of educational qualification on customer awareness of wearable devices as the p-value is equal to 0.215 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

H2: Monthly Income have an impact on the customer awareness of wearable devices

Table 1.5 Descriptive statistics: effects of the personal monthly income of respondents to awareness of wearable devices

Descriptives								
WearableDevice	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
					1.0	25		
2.0	9	3.11	1.054	.351	2.30	3.92	2	5
3.0	20	3.30	1.174	.263	2.75	3.85	2	5
4.0	16	3.13	1.025	.256	2.58	3.67	1	5
5.0	49	3.08	1.057	.151	2.78	3.39	1	5
6.0	44	3.66	.914	.138	3.38	3.94	2	5
Total	163	3.36	1.040	.081	3.19	3.52	1	5

ANOVA					
WearableDevice	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Within Groups	164.159	157	1.046		
Total	175.362	162			

Table 1.6 Testing Hypothesis using ANOVA

Similar to the first hypothesis, a one-way ANOVA between subjects was conducted to compare the effects of the personal monthly income of respondents to awareness of wearable devices. We chose ANOVA because it is an appropriate test for multiple test subjects. There was a significant effect of educational qualification on customer awareness of wearable devices as the p-value is equal to 0.063 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

H3: There is no significant difference in awareness of wearable devices of people owning a health insurance policy.

Table 1.7 Descriptive Statistics: The effects of degree of education on awareness of wearable devices

Group Statistics

Do you own a health insurance policy		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Wearable Device	1.0	125	3.34	1.039	.093
	2.0	38	3.42	1.056	.171

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Wearable Device									
Equal variances assumed	.126	.723	-.440	161	.660	-.085	.193	-.467	.297
Equal variances not assumed			-.436	60.424	.664	-.085	.195	-.475	.305

Table 1.8: Testing Hypothesis using independent samples t-test

An independent t-test was conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the awareness of wearable devices among people who own a health insurance policy. The results indicated that there is not a significant difference between the group that owns a health insurance policy (yes coded as 1.0) (M=3.340; SD=1.039) and the group that does not own a health insurance policy (M=3.420; SD=1.056); p=0.660. As the p-value is greater than 0.05, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis.

The respondents were asked what kind of gadgets they use to track their health as their leading tool. The replies gathered are displayed in Figure 1.3. The smartphone is by far the most commonly utilized device, which is understandable given that most phones include apps that automatically track metrics like distance traveled, hours slept, and steps are taken. The next best responses were followed by smartwatches and fit-bit devices. Due to the fact, the options given were not mutually exclusive, the respondents had the liberty to choose more than one wearable device as their preferred tracking device. No response was obtained for Google glass and GPS shoes showing the low rate of usage of these products. It is because these devices are comparatively new to the market. About 29% of respondents indicated they don't track any of their health-related data.

Fig 1.3 Distribution of results by the wearable device used

Incentives for by using a wearable device

The respondents were asked what are the incentives they look for by using the wearable devices on a 5-point Likert scale (1 being least important and 5 being most important) the options ranged from early detection of diseases to just fitness tracking. The average of the responses for each option was taken and compared. See table 1.9 below .

Table 1.9 Incentives to adopt wearables

Incentives	Average Score
Better healthy lifestyle	3.914
Early detection of diseases	3.644
Personalized insurance (Lesser premium for good lifestyle)	3.331
Fitness tracking	4.012
Prediction of future health risks	3.766

The results imply that most of the respondents are willing to adopt the wearables provided they get the necessary information on fitness tracking. This result is because people consider using wearables for the main purpose of tracking their fitness activities. A better healthy lifestyle was the next opted incentive out of the 5 options.

Individuals who already live a healthy lifestyle and wish to track their development are more likely to buy wearables right now. The bulk of wearable device manufacturers (such as Fitbit, Jawbone, and Nike) emphasize their gadgets' ability to serve as an "all-in-one" platform for boosting physical performance and forming positive habits. To increase user engagement, wearable manufacturers employ a variety of digital persuasive techniques and social influence strategies, such as gamification of activity through competitions and challenges, publication of visible feedback on performance based on social influence principles, or reinforcements in the form of virtual rewards for achievements. Several scientific and popular publications suggest how to use consumer wearables as "self-hacking" devices to improve sleep, control stress, and boost productivity.

Sharing Personal Data with Insurers

As shown in Figure 1.4, respondents were asked how they thought about insurers having access to their wearable data. Only 41.7% of the respondents said they would disclose any kind of tracking data to their insurers, and 20.9 % of respondents felt they wouldn't share the tracking data with insurers. Also, a big percentage of respondents (about 37.4%) are not sure about the sharing of data which points to the lack of awareness among them. The participants' biggest worries appear to be that data from wearables could affect their insurance premiums or the security of their personal information. See figure 1.4 below.

Fig 1.4 Sharing the tracking data with insurers

The main reason behind the insecurity in sharing the data is found to be that most of the respondents don't want the data they shared to be used as part of their insurance premium, they believe the tracking data will harm the premium.

It's found that simply providing a wearable to a policyholder and waiting for him or her to boost their health results is insufficient. Concurrent customized coaching should be provided for real-time improvement status and analysis of data collected. It will be a win-win situation only when this happens for both policyholders and insurers. In health insurance, the use of wearable data will play a crucial role in risk management and risk rating. At present, insurers only have access

to data of limited quantity. This data is collected at a specific point in time by medical examinations or self-reporting acknowledgments, those are frequently not adequate for risk management on a continuous evaluation.

The respondents were asked whether they agreed that wearable data should be used to establish health insurance premiums at the beginning of the insurance policy in a Likert scale option. (1 being Strongly disagreed and 5 being Strongly agreed). 31.3 % of the respondents had only a neutral agreement to the question. This may be because the respondents are reluctant to answer as they have less awareness about the application of the wearable in insurance premiums and their implications. About 27 % of respondents strongly agreed that wearable device data should be used to fix premiums at the beginning of health insurance policies. 11 % had a strong disagreement with the statement. See figure 1.5 showing the details below.

Fig 1.5 Use of wearables for a premium loading

The final question that the respondents were asked was about the likelihood of renewal of their existing insurance policy if the insurer supplied them with a free wearable for a year. Unsurprisingly the majority (about 35.6 %) answered they are very likely to renew the policy. The spectrum of responses is in favor of the motion that people are willing to renew the policy if they get a free wearable from the insurer.

Wearables assist the medical and health insurance industries by delivering solutions to human health behavior in this part. In addition, we see AI and wearables being used in the healthcare and insurance industries for a variety of use cases and applications that aid in the monitoring of various parameters.

Wearable devices will have an impact on every step of the insurance buyer's experience. At various phases of the value chain, the wearable ecosystem will have several touchpoints. As

more individuals begin to use wearable devices, they will become increasingly popular. The health insurance value chain, which is a part of their daily lives, is going to change in some of the methods for gathering data via the use of wearable devices.

Wearables will have a significant impact on the insurer's Front Office, starting with user experience and progressing to non-intrusive data collection and effective engagement with the insured. It will be simple to identify the needs of existing insurance clients using the data obtained at this stage. The information can also be utilized to create new client groups.

Insurers can research risk behaviors and advertise goods to each client segment using the information gathered from customers. Insurers' target-market strategies will benefit from this enabling technology.

The analysis for new pricing models based on fresh data inputs from wearable devices will be done under Policy Administration and Underwriting. By assessing the continuous flow of real-time risk-surrogate data, these will be used to determine premiums. As a result of the activities undertaken by clients seeking a healthier lifestyle, premiums may rise or fall. This will boost decision-making capability, allowing for more accurate risk evaluations and pricing. Insurers will be able to profit from the increased availability of insurance float for investments as a result of improved predictability. Furthermore, policyholder service will handle all interactions related to putting systems in place to reduce risks by raising warning signals in the case of a sudden unfavorable health condition. This will aid insurers in their efforts to boost customer involvement, as well as their chances of preventing consumers from experiencing a risk event.

When a notification is delivered in the event of an accident, the claims management process will begin. It will also screen for potential frauds, minimize claim expenses, and improve claim issuing turnaround time. The claims procedure could shift from a reacting-to-risk paradigm to a preventing-the-risk strategy.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to examine how AI-enabled smart wearables are being used in the field of healthcare, specifically health insurance. It helps the healthcare system determine a person's health status, exercise habits, and early disease prediction to improve future health. It demonstrates how an insurance company may use a wearable device to change customer interactions to increase revenue and profits. This project will assist researchers, insurance domain specialists, and healthcare practitioners in determining how data collected from end users might be leveraged to deliver value to customers and insurance corporations by establishing a health-aware ecosystem. This, however, will be hampered by the need to handle privacy concerns.

It can also aid in the elimination of false claims and the speedy and reasonable settlement of claims, as well as examine the far-reaching effects. Wearable IoT has the potential to offer up a flood of new opportunities. However, there is currently little evidence that wearable gadgets

will have an impact on policyholder behavior. There's also some evidence that statistics gathered by wearable data today will have a significant impact on health in the future, and it's important to note that wearables aren't likely to be effective in driving real changes in daily lifestyles and changing member's health paradigms on their own. While wearables supply inputs related to a healthy lifestyle and therefore potential loading variables for underwriting and premium pricing, each ostensible benefit comes with its own set of hazards, and the added ramifications of merging the pieces of data may not be justified. Certain concerns, such as tracking erroneous or fraudulent data, must be handled. In addition, the variety of data from multiple devices is a problem. The respondents in a study on the function of wearables in health insurance were surprised to learn that they were wearing them.

A survey of the most important research efforts in the field of wearables was done as part of the study. Wearables hold a lot of promise once an integrated IoT system is available. As a result, the actual potential of combining wearables with IoT has gone untapped. While real-time data has a lot of potential, it should be handled with caution because of the significant risk of fraud, huge potential costs for insurers, skepticism about data veracity, and questions about fairness in how this translates into pricing and underwriting actions that affect individual members.

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